

MAGPIE: Mission for Advanced Geophysics and Polar Ice Exploration – Mission Overview S. C. Casanova¹, A. Hutton¹, S. Sanchez¹ ¹ispace Europe - Rue de l'Industrie 5, Paul Wurth InCub, 1811 Luxembourg

Introduction: The Mission for Advanced Geophysics and Polar Ice Exploration (MAGPIE) is a European-led lunar rover mission funded by ESA and developed by ispace Europe in collaboration with academic and institutional partners. The mission targets scientifically valuable terrains in the lunar south polar region to investigate volatile occurrence, subsurface structure, and local environmental processes. MAGPIE is designed to address key priorities outlined in ESA's Strategy for Science at the Moon and contributes to broader goals under ESA's 2040 strategic vision.

Scientific Motivation: Permanently shadowed regions (PSRs) near the lunar poles are among the coldest environments in the Solar System, capable of cold-trapping volatiles over geological timescales. While long duration access into PSRs is beyond the reach of compact solar-powered rovers, MAGPIE is capable of exploring adjacent accessible terrains, including seasonally shadowed regions, micro cold traps, and partially illuminated slopes. These environments exhibit dynamic thermal cycles and may preserve transient volatiles or partially buried deposits. Understanding the interactions between volatile distribution, terrain evolution, and environmental forcing is central to advancing lunar polar science and preparing for future exploration and ISRU activities.

Science Goals: MAGPIE's investigations are framed around three overarching science goals:

1. Characterise the occurrence and properties of polar water ice and other volatiles.
2. Analyse near-surface geology and geophysical structure.
3. Monitor the local surface environment and its processes.

These goals establish a coordinated framework linking volatile behaviour to regolith structure, surface modification processes, and environmental conditions.

Payload and Measurement Strategy: MAGPIE carries a compact complementary payload suite provided by European research institutions:

- **Neutron HardPix Spectrometer:** (IEAP, Czech Republic) for mapping hydrogen abundance.
- **Lunar RIMFAX Ground Penetrating Radar:** (CENSSS, Norway) for resolving

subsurface stratigraphy and identifying buried features such as blocks or layered structures.

- **Lunar Volatiles Scout Drill and Ion Trap Mass Spectrometer** (TUM, Germany; Open University, UK) for shallow sampling and evolved gas analysis to detect volatile species.

This integrated approach enables assessment of hydrogen distribution, volatile release behaviour, near-surface layering, and environmental context.

Mission Context and ispace Rover Development: MAGPIE is built on ispace's rover development roadmap. The micro Rover (uRover), flown on ispace's M2, provides heritage for avionics and mobility systems. The MAGPIE concept uses the larger Exploration Class Rover (xRover), capable of carrying multiple payloads and operating over greater distances. This platform enables MAGPIE to deliver high-priority science within a compact, commercially provided mission envelope.

Conclusion: MAGPIE demonstrates how a coordinated partnership between commercial industry, ESA, and European research institutions can deliver high-value lunar science while maturing technologies and operational capabilities for future exploration. Its integrated measurements will advance understanding of polar volatiles, subsurface structure, and environmental processes, and will inform the design of future infrastructure and ISRU concepts at the Moon.